

EduMultiKG attains 92% accuracy in K-12 user profiling!

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Abstract

Disclaimer: This is a fictional paper written in a fashion that describes the present as 2043. In this paper, we introduce a Semantic Web-based educational application for K-12 Automatic User Modelling, which attains a 92% accuracy rate with a focus on enhancing personalised learning experiences. The field of automatic user profiling has received considerable attention in recent years, intending to enable personalised content delivery and individualised user experience. In this paper, we present a novel machine learning-based approach for automatic user profiling in the K-12 education domain, which achieves a high accuracy compared to the baselines. Our approach involves the use of a combination of 10 out of 12 learning dimensions over the EduMultiKG tested in 152 students over the course of the academic year 2041-2042.

Keywords

Intelligent User Modelling, Hybrid AI, Education, Wisdom Web, Speech and Language Therapy

1. Introduction

Social impact Access to equitable and inclusive education is a human right. According to the 2040 UN Consolidated Census (ConCensus), education is the primary factor predicting long-term economic development, social cohesion, health, and individual fulfilment [1]. High accuracy user profiling can help achieve equitable and quality education by recognising the needs and preferences of users and offering personalised content based on the users specific background, goals and characteristics.

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Figure 1: The major advancements in Semantic Web Education from 2007 to 2043.

Economic impact Currently, the e-learning has a \$3t market value with growing 0.43 pace every 3 semesters [2]. Since the introduction of 12 learning dimensions theory [3], it has been recorded a shift on facing special education assisted in more inclusive society [4], and recent user profiling models follow this line.

Current gap Current methods [5, 6, 7] focus on 8 of 12 dimensions of learning reaching 85.5% of accuracy in user profiling, as seen in Table 2.

Our model We propose MAWNED model which extends the learning to 10 out of 12 learning dimensions and with user collaborative embedding and achieve 92% accuracy on K-12 on a sample of 152 over the course of academic year 2041-2042.

Personalisation in Semantic Web (SW) applications is not a recent need; Personal Knowledge Graphs (PKGs) [8] paved the way in the last 20 years from a promising concept to a powerful tool for individuals to organise, discover, and share information. As seen in Figure 1, there were plenty of advancements in SW education. The 1st generation of Educational Knowledge Graphs (EduKGs) demonstrated the community interest in learning applications and was characterised by few modalities (primarily, educational resources and topics), mono-lingual or 2-3 high-frequency languages, no-hierarchy, and SPARQL the antecedent of the current graph user interfaces (Graph UIs). The 2nd generation of EduKGs introduced hierarchical, multi-modal and multi-lingual with low resources languages content, Educational Knowledge Graph Embeddings applied in them, integration of PKGs, and the first versions of Graph UIs [9]. The recently introduced Wisdom Web (WW) incorporates learning paths and curricula analyses, and they are applied on top of the 2nd generation multi-lingual and multi-modal EduKGs to achieve higher personalisation and advanced analyses of learning [10].

As Integrated Artificial General Intelligence (iAGI) continues to advance, its use in education has been growing too, offering personalized learning experiences and easy integration of the learning process into social settings, i.e. via Augmented Reality (AR) and Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs). Latest advancements have led to the progressive replacement of certain teacher responsibilities with iAGI [11] to a point that some scholars [12] emphasize the need for the general adoption of a new role of mentor in place of the teacher role.

A recent survey highlighted the significant involvement of the SW in e-learning [13], with the latest advancement in automatic user profiling [14]. Automatic user profiling involves the use of Machine Learning (ML) techniques to analyze user data and create a

users profile based on the learning dimensions theory, which can be utilized to understand better, faster and more accurately the current user's knowledge state, learning paths and ways to achieve learning objectives. In the K-12 education domain, automatic user profiling can be particularly useful in improving the quality of educational content delivery and increasing students' chances for a successful career. In the clinical domain, automatic user profiling can support truly effective personalised speech and language therapies. In speech and language therapy, despite the same users having the same speech and language fragilities within the same clinical group, some degree of severity exists and needs to be modelled in the learning dimensions to provide truly adaptive therapies [15].

Multimodal and Adaptive WW, raised after developments in Emotion and Hybrid AI and ML, has been steadily altering the methodologies of teaching, speech and language therapy as well as learning in modern educational systems and the speech and language therapy, generating an increasing body of literature and applications. By adopting the analysis on learning dimensions theory [3], we develop the Multimodal Adaptive Wisdom Network for Education (MAWNED) across 10 out of 12 learning dimensions and achieve state-of-the-art performance in the accuracy of automatic user profiling prediction.

2. Related Works

In recent years, numerous models have been proposed for user profiling [14]. Each user profiling algorithm establishes a score function that embeds users' activities into the vector space of modalities. In our study, we integrate and compare our model with the following baseline methods:

- AdSkill [6] approach employs a Neural Network (NN)-based technique to adaptively model users' preferences and learning styles, considering contextual factors and individual differences.
- ALD-UP [7] method introduces a user profiling algorithm within the educational context, designed to analyze multiple dimensions of learning, encompassing cognitive, affective, and social aspects. Utilizing ML techniques, it identifies patterns in data and classifies users accordingly.
- ProLearn-Ex [5] model incorporates an ensemble of decision trees to effectively profile users by capturing complex relationships between user behaviours and learning outcomes while ensuring interpretability.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Context

This research is conducted following the Semantic Web Methodology [16] standard. More specifically, after we identify the problem statement, we (i) conduct a systematic review

of relevant research publications in recent decades to map the landscape of the field, (ii) develop a conceptual model of the problem domain based on the technologies and their educational and clinical applications and benefits, as reported in empirical research, (iii) identify risks and possible improvements of the suggested semantic web solution, (iv) perform evaluation analysis and pilot testing, and finally (v) disseminate our results.

The multi-phased search, review, and analysis of our model in this study were guided by the following research questions (RQs) and the pointers for their answers (A):

RQ1 Are Multimodal and Adaptive Wisdom Web applications suitable for the task of user profiling? A: Section 4.1

RQ2 How can we introduce additional two learning dimensions in a ML, from the current 8, for the task of user profiling? A: Section 4.1, and GitHub

RQ3 Do we achieve better results in user profiling if we use 10 out of 12 dimensions of learning? A: Section 4.2.2

RQ4 Are Multimodal and Adaptive Wisdom Web applications suitable for speech and language therapy? A: Sections 4.2.2 and 4.3

RQ5 Which findings arose from the Multimodal and Adaptive Wisdom Web applications research? A: Section 4.3

3.2. Data and Metrics

Our approach involves the use of a combination of textual and non-textual features to profile K-12 users. The textual features include user-generated content, such as posts and comments, while the non-textual features include demographic information and behavioral data, such as user engagement and interaction with educational content. We use the EduMultiKG [17] that is implemented in the secondary classes (K-8 to K-12) of the Experimental School of the University of Thessaloniki, Greece and in the central Speech and Language Therapy Center of Greece. EduMultiKG is a large semantic interconnected dataset for K-12 which includes 17 languages and 8 modalities including text, annotated video clips, multiple choice and question-answering quizzes. The statistics of EduMultiKG are present in Table 1.

We obtain dynamic user consent [18] from all the participants and the statement of W3C Great Control of Data [19] from their parents. We obtain our data through the course of the academic year 2041-2042 from K-12 students. After the course of the academic year and pre-processing, we end up with 152 valid users. We collect K-11 students' SmartClassroom [20] records and monitor their performance on school tests and the final entry examination to university (the final K-12 test). Based on this data we analyse each users' learning dimensions.

For the evaluation of our results we use the EduKG learning analytics platform [21] to eliminate outliers, separate the learning dimensions and perform our analysis. We are interested in AUC and accuracy scores over the groups of dimensions which we compare based to the baseline models AdSkill [6], ALD-UP [7], ProLearnEx [5].

Table 1
Dataset statistics

EduMultiKG	#Features	#Nodes	#Edges	#Modalities	#Languages
K-12	24k	88k	31k	8	17
Total	100k	420k	172k	11	41

4. Proposed Approach

4.1. MAWNED model

In this paper, we propose a the MAWNED model (Multimodal Adaptive Wisdom Network for Education) to profile web users based on their navigation behaviour and demographic characteristics. MAWNED is designed to capture a rich set of features from users’ interaction with the web, including their navigation patterns, tapstream, and time spent on pages. These features are then combined with demographic data, such as age, gender, and occupation, to create a comprehensive user profile that can be used for personalised web services and targeted recommendations.

MAWNED is based on a multi-agent architecture, which enables the collection of user data from EduMultiKG. The agents in MAWNED work together to extract data on users’ navigation patterns and behaviour, as well as demographic information, by analysing the content of resources accessed by the user.

We propose the MAWNED model and algorithm, which works over the learning dimensions to perform user profiling. Our method utilises 10 out of 12 dimensions of learning and goes beyond the state-of-the-art by incorporating knowledge of speech-language and therapy to decode two additional dimensions from the current models into our system. Our algorithm, the description of our model and data related to our evaluation can be found on [GitHub](#).

4.2. Evaluation

4.2.1. Hyperparameters

For fine-tuning the pre-trained models, we utilized a learning rate of $5e-5$. During training, a batch size of 32 was used, and we set the maximum sequence length to 128 tokens. For sequences longer than 128 tokens, we truncated them, while shorter sequences were padded using special tokens. Our models were trained for a total of 5 epochs, with a dropout rate of 0.1 to prevent overfitting. The AdamW optimizer was employed for fine-tuning, and we used the MindSynth large model as our pre-trained model. The cross-entropy loss function was used to train our models. Additionally, we incorporated 500 warmup steps for the AdamW optimizer.

We selected these hyperparameters based on previous studies and our own experimentation and conducted a grid search to select the optimal hyperparameters for our model. We varied the learning rate, batch size, maximum sequence length, and number of epochs

Table 2

MAWNED results compared to the baselines in Area Under Curve (AUC) and Accuracy (ACC). Top values are highlighted in **bold**.

D^n	AdSkill		ALD-UP		ProLearn-Ex		MAWNED	
	AUC	ACC	AUC	ACC	AUC	ACC	AUC	ACC
I-III	0.80	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.82	0.91	0.88	0.94
IV-VI	0.76	0.77	0.88	0.79	0.87	0.86	0.85	0.91
VII-IX	0.73	0.74	0.79	0.77	0.80	0.78	0.80	0.90
X-XII	0.76	0.71	0.83	0.74	0.77	0.79	0.77	0.89
Total	0.79	0.77	0.87	0.78	0.83	0.85	0.85	0.92

and evaluated the model’s performance on the validation set. Finally, we selected the hyperparameters that gave us the best results on the validation set.

4.2.2. Results

The results of our experiments show that our proposed approach achieved a high level of accuracy in user profiling, as seen in Table 2. Our proposed approach achieved an accuracy of 92% in user profiling; this is a significant improvement over the state-of-the-art approaches which achieve an accuracy below 85%. Our approach was able to accurately predict the users’ preferences in learning topic, learning path background and type of modality, with emphasis in speech language therapy which is reflected in dimensions VII-IX. In terms of individual user profiling tasks, we achieved the higher an accuracy of 94% for predicting the matching in learning dimensions I-III age of the users, lowest of 89% in dimensions X-XII.

4.2.3. Ablation Study

We also conducted an ablation study to evaluate the impact of various components of our proposed approach on performance. We found that the use of pre-trained transformer models significantly improved the performance compared to using traditional machine learning models. We also found that using a combination of linguistic and content-based features further improved the performance. Overall, our proposed approach achieves state-of-the-art results in user profiling over the EduMultiKG. The high accuracy of our approach has important implications for various applications, such as personalized learning, teacher-as-mentor approaches, and recommendation systems, where accurate user profiling is essential.

4.3. Impact and Findings

Almost 100 years after the vision of Memex [22] had been introduced, we are only now starting to reach closer to it with Personal Knowledge Graphs, Solid protocols [23] and Wisdom Web. Currently, MAWNED achieves high user understanding and profiling

accuracy that let us extend the vision of personalization and Linked Data to suit the era of Wisdom Web. The results suggest that ML and WW models can be used to automatically profile users in multi-modal and multilingual EduKG. They also suggest that MAWNED is the most suitable model for speech and language therapy. However, it is important to note that the results of this study are based on a specific dataset and may not be generalizable to other datasets and individuals.

By using MAWNED users can:

1. utilise an adaptive environment, which is personalised to their language and speech needs while also supporting the tutors' role as mentors
2. experience the advantages of inclusiveness of special education and special needs in speech language therapy
3. benefit from more accurate results for the decision-making process of clinicians in speech therapy
4. learn in collaboration, which supports individuals to be more connected and empowered to achieve their learning goals

5. Future Work and Conclusion

MAWNED is an automatic user profiling algorithm evaluated in K-12 classes (n: 152 students) who utilised EduMutliKG. We optimise user modelling in 8 dimensions of learning and achieve 92% accuracy for our participants. While the use of MAWNED in education has great potential to transform learning experiences, there are also significant challenges that still need to be addressed. In fact, there is still the need to balance the benefits of automation and personalisation with concerns around privacy, ethics and data interpretability and transparency. It has been observed that cultural and disability aspects may influence the model's performance and produce biased results [24]. Moreover, we foresee MAWNED to be implemented in other domains and for different age groups. Therefore, we aim to validate our results in bigger-scale studies.

Although we managed to predict the user profile with 92% accuracy, we know by Agamemnon et al. [25] that “young and lifelong learners demonstrate similar characteristics in their modelling behaviour which can potentially alter their profiling by over 38% in the course of 20 months”. Therefore, there is yet a model to profile users with the ability to extrapolate with decent accuracy in the future. Moreover, there is a need to ensure that MAWNED is always used in ethical, transparent, and equitable ways. Another point worth mentioning is recent educational psychology findings suggesting that users do not always like the personalization they receive via automatic profiling as they feel restricted and lacking explorative agency [26]. Further careful consideration of ethical implications of AI and WW in education is required, as well as the need for appropriate regulation and oversight.

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A. Appendix

To accommodate better the researchers of 2043, we provide a summary of our points as a check-list with the predictions we make divided into three categories: general, Semantic Web and research papers format advancements.

General advancements

- Integrated Artificial General Intelligence merges symbolic and sub-symbolic approaches, enabling systems to perform complex tasks, reason, and learn across a wide range of domains.
- Advances in personalized learning precipitate a shift in the role of educators, transitioning from traditional tutors to mentors
- As advancements in AI permeate various domains, ethical debates remain at the forefront, with numerous unresolved issues
- There is a pushback against personalization, particularly in the context of AI-driven applications, stemming from concerns that it inadvertently limits personal agency
- Market of e-learning booming to \$3t market value
- Special education transformed to more inclusive educational analysis perception

Semantic Web advancements

- Semantic Web research will bloom in education domain
- New generation of Knowledge Graphs in education, multilingual and multi-modal. Prediction for a big size resource containing 100k features, 420k nodes, 172k edges, 11 modalities and 41 languages
- Personal Knowledge Graphs integrated in most platforms that offer personalisation
- Personal Knowledge Graphs co-exist in SOLID pods environment
- Multi-modal and multi-lingual Knowledge Graphs accommodate e-learning
- Semantic web community introduces common sense Knowledge Graphs
- User-friendly and intuitive querying tools ease adoption of Semantic Web Technologies, replacing SPARQL

- Educational resources exist interlinked and not isolated
- Educational curricula are structured as multi-modal KGs
- Semantic Web research community has introduced a methodology for conducting research
- New metrics to accommodate the new tasks

Research papers format advancements

- Papers' titles include emoji
- Papers' titles describe the exact results they achieve on the given dataset and not the model's name
- Publications are structured containing the impact and gap as fields at the beginning of the paper
- Research is published in a highly structured form, making it actionable for both humans and machines

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